

D6.5 GUIDELINES FOR INDUSTRIAL TAKE UP – TECHNICAL, SAFETY AND PRACTICAL GUIDELINES TO SUPPORT CIRCULAR USE OF PE PCR FOR THE SAME FLEXIBLE FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATION AGAIN

WORK PACKAGE 6

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
Amcor-G	Amcor Flexible in Gent
Amcor-K	Amcor Flexible in Kreuzlingen
COF	Coefficient of friction
EU	European Union
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
FCA	Food contact application
IVV	Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging (IVV)
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
LSIT	Lowest Seal Initiation Temperature
MDOPE	Machine-direction oriented Polyethylene
MFI	Melt flow index
nFCA	Non-food contact application
OTR	Oxygen transmission rate
PC	Post-consumer
PCR	Post-consumer recyclates
PE	Polyethylene
rPE	Recycled Polyethylene
SF	Solvent-free
SUP	Stand-up pouch
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WP	Work package
WVTR	Water vapour transmission rate

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of Workpackage (WP) 6 is to demonstrate and validate the circularity of flexible food and non-food packaging. This work package focuses on three distinct loop scenarios to showcase how recycled materials from different waste sources can be reused in innovative packaging applications. It further evaluates the quality of post-consumer recyclates (PCRs) produced through the recycling cascades established in WP 3 and applied in WP 6.

In “Loop 1,” flexible household polyethylene (PE)-rich packaging waste is targeted as input. By employing an optimized cascade of pre-treatment, dissolution-based recycling, and post-treatment technologies, the quality of PE PCRs is significantly improved, enabling their reuse in film applications for home care and personal care packaging.

“Loop 2” explores a closed-loop business-to-business (B2B) collection system for flexible food packaging. This closed system, combined with an appropriate recycling cascade, allows recycled materials to be reused in food packaging applications.

“Loop 3” consists of two cycles designed to simulate the repeated use of recycled materials in packaging and to assess the impact of a second recycling step on material properties. This scenario focuses on food packaging applications and employs tracer-based sorting (TBS) to separate food packaging items from real household mixed food and non-food packaging waste. The sorted food packaging items are then recycled using various cascades developed in WP3, which are carefully evaluated and selected to ensure the highest possible recyclate quality for reuse in food packaging.

In total, six packaging demonstrators were produced, representing three use cases: food packaging, home care packaging, and personal care packaging. At least three different laminate structures for flexible packaging were developed and produced using the PE-PCRs from the three loops described above, with contributions from project partners AMCOR, NESTLE, Fraunhofer, SIEGWERK, and Polysecure. These demonstrators showcase the value chain and technologies necessary to achieve and demonstrate circularity in flexible packaging.

This deliverable provides technical, safety, and practical guidelines to support the circular use of PE PCRs in flexible food packaging. It includes sections on sorting, pre-treatments in combination with physical recycling, safety aspects, design for and from recycling, Life Cycle Sustainability Assessments, and market perspectives. Additionally, it offers recommendations for overcoming technical, financial, and regulatory barriers, aiming to enhance recycling efficiency, particularly for plastic food packaging materials.

ABBREVIATIONS

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SUP	Stand-up pouch
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WP	Work package
WVTR	Water vapour transmission rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Recycling plays a crucial role in reducing environmental impacts, especially in the context of food packaging. Among packaging materials, plastic has the highest carbon intensity. Recycling flexible plastic packaging waste is significantly more effective at mitigating climate change impacts than incineration with energy recovery—up to five times more effective in reducing CO₂ emissions (kg CO₂-eq./t)¹. Consequently, the upcoming Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) sets targets for recycled content in packaging, including food packaging². However, the recycling industry still faces challenges, particularly in achieving sufficient purification efficiency with current sorting and recycling technologies. Addressing these barriers is crucial for promoting sustainable practices and achieving recycling targets. This deliverable provides guidelines for the circularity of food packaging, outlines key findings and proposes actionable strategies to overcome challenges, ensuring the advancement of sustainable recycling practices in accordance with PPWR of the European Commission.

Starting from post-consumer flexible packaging waste streams established in Europe, the project has tested combinations of advanced sorting and purification methods to separate materials and compounds from waste packaging considered harmful in production of sensitive packaging. In addition, mono-material packaging concepts were designed to encounter recyclability and material safety while implementing purified post-consumer polyethylene recyclates (PE PCR). Developments were accompanied by studies to ensure food compliance, sustainability and economy.

This deliverable is the outcome of Task T6.5 “Implementation by packaging and lifetime tests, evaluation and guidelines for industrial take-up”. In Task 6.5, food package production has been performed at the project partner NESTLE, and non-food packaging at AMCOR with the novel PE based mono-material laminates produced at AMCOR. Mechanical and barrier tests, compliance performance, and shelf-life predictions have been realized on-site according to the end-user’s specifications at AMCOR, Fraunhofer, and NESTLE, respectively. Results have been evaluated and compared for each 3 Use Cases, i.e. food, home and personal care packaging, with 6 demonstrators in total (3 for food and 3 for non-food packaging), including economical assessments, and LCSA from WP7.

Through this research project, CIRCULAR FoodPack partners demonstrated that combining tracing systems in sorting with properly implemented “advanced physical recycling”, which includes technologies such as delamination/deinking or dissolution-based recycling, is a viable, cost-effective, and efficient method for recycling packaging waste into flexible films for contact-sensitive applications, offering a strong alternative to virgin materials. To promote circularity in flexible plastic food packaging, the project partners identified seven key areas as essential and developed solutions and strategies to address the challenges within these areas.

These are:

- 1) Sorting
- 2) Purification and recycling through advanced mechanical processes and dissolution

¹ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC132067>

² https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:de4f236d-7164-11ed-9887-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

- 3) Design for and from recycling for circularity of food packaging value chain
- 4) Safety aspects
- 5) Implementation of circularity into food packaging value chain
- 6) Consumer acceptance and market demand
- 7) Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA)

The deliverable covers these topics and provides guidelines and recommendations for scaling up sorting processes, advancing the physical recycling (or advanced mechanical recycling) of polyethylene (PE) for food packaging, and incorporating design strategies both for recycling and from recycled materials, with a focus on safety considerations. These guidelines aim to support the development of more efficient recycling systems and foster the adoption of sustainable practices in the packaging industry. They encourage "production" and "marketing" to adopt new approaches that promote the use of sortable, recyclable, and functional flexible food packaging materials. Additionally, the recommendations address ways to offset the anticipated (marginally) higher costs associated with the innovative CIRCULAR FoodPack-based products, providing a roadmap for achieving circularity in food packaging while ensuring safety, quality, and market viability.

2. SORTING

- Within CIRCULAR FoodPack, it has been demonstrated that Tracer-Based-Sorting (TBS) allows to identify freely definable types of packaging and divert it from the waste stream. In this way a specific stream can be created and isolated from the rest of the packaging waste (e.g. food packaging from non-food, laminates from single ply, specialty packaging from other packaging, etc...). In the frame of the project, a tracer was embedded in parts of the packaging printing by incorporating it into the printing ink, which has the advantage that the tracer can then be washed off within the deinking, purification and/or physical recycling steps (such as the dissolution process). An advantage of TBS is that it can be applied as an upgrade to existing sorting facilities. If the detection technology implemented in the near-infrared sorters of the facility is suitable, the upgrade is a low-cost solution. At least seven freely assignable tracer codes are available. However, as an upgrade TBS uses up one existing sorting stage per fraction.
- With TBS, very high sorting purities of >98% can be reached, as has been demonstrated in the project in sorting trials at industrial scale. At a TRL (technology readiness level) of currently 6 for the TBS solution with upgraded Near-Infrared Radiation (NIR) sorters, the technology is ready to be upscaled and integrated in pilot sorting lines.
- The tracer technology is compatible with existing conversion techniques such as rotogravure printing. This technique was used in this project both on pilot scale and on industrial scale. Hereby the tracer elements are simply mixed in with the ink formulation and can be embedded invisibly in the existing print design in this way. A guideline on applying the tracers to ensure sufficient detection has been published in Deliverable D3.8, "Guidelines on Design for Recycling". The technique to embed the tracers in the ink formulation implies that the converter does not need to invest by a great deal to implement the technology. Usually, no extra cylinder is needed to implement tracers and no drastic change in print design is needed to enable recognition (in contrast to e.g. QR codes, which impose a visible change to the packaging design).
- TBS can be applied as an upgrade to existing sorting facilities with capital investment costs around 10k Euro (per meter belt) width to upgrade conventional NIR sorting machines. By limiting the overall processing cost to 20€ Euro per ton of waste, the added sales value generated on the recovered waste far outweighs the initial cost add on.
- TBS is a clear step beyond the state of the art in flexible packaging sorting, as neither NIR nor Artificial Intelligence (AI) provide reliable identification of flexible packaging in all cases: NIR only identifies the main polymer type and cannot detect non-material-inherent categories, whereas AI-based object recognition and classification approaches have difficulties to 'recognize' films (in contrast to rigids where AI can potentially be more effective).
- An approach alternative to implementing tracers in existing NIR lines is the Sort4Circle® (S4C) process. S4C relies on the singulation of waste items, followed by measurement of all relevant parameters for each item and subsequent sorting to an arbitrary number of fractions according to the combined measurement result. This means that a single detection system is used to scan items. Such a detection may include tracer recognition as well as conventional NIR spectroscopy, color measurement, mid-infrared for black polymers, AI based object

recognition or any other suitable technology. Such a system allows more cost-effective separation of streams that should be separated in multiple fractions since the cost does not scale with the number of fractions (instead of current NIR sorters that can only split streams in two). This is especially relevant for films, which might be separated in many different types (food/non-food, monolayer, ink type, all multilayer types, etc.).

- S4C lab trials within the project have shown **purities of the sorted fractions** (two traced, one non-traced fraction) **of 99% with yields of 96%**. Current TRL is at 5-6. The improved key figures are achieved due to no losses in the mechanical handling of the singulated objects and better measurement conditions.
- In addition to TBS, the project investigated advanced Sensor-Based-Specification (SBS) to improve the sorting purity of flexible packaging waste streams without tracers. A prototype SBS setup was developed, featuring an NIR hyperspectral imaging camera integrated with a machine-learning-based analysis algorithm. It has been shown that SBS, combined with advanced analysis techniques, can further enhance the purity of a PE-rich flexible waste output stream from a conventional sorting site by up to 8%. Particularly promising is the technology's ability to detect specific multimaterial-multilayer types, such as PET/PE or PA/PE laminates, thereby potentially reducing contamination from foreign materials in the PE-rich flexible packaging waste input.

In summary, CIRCULAR FoodPack has proven that (TBS) is a versatile and material-independent solution for achieving high-purity separation of traced flexible packaging, regardless of the equipment used. This approach offers a significant advantage over current technologies and AI-based innovations, which face greater challenges with flexible packaging. TBS systems provide the packaging industry with a cost-efficient and reliable method to sort food and other specific flexible packaging types, aligning with the requirements of the new PPWR and other circularity objectives. By enabling a closed-loop recycling system with sorting purity levels of up to 99%, TBS facilitates the integration of produced post-consumer recycled materials (PCRs) back into food packaging applications, advancing sustainability goals according to the regulations³.

³ COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2022/1616 of 15 September 2022 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 282/2008

3. PURIFICATION AND RECYCLING THROUGH ADVANCED MECHANICAL PROCESSES AND DISSOLUTION

Current state-of-the-art mechanical recycling infrastructure does not separate inks or multilayers, which impedes closed loop recycling, amongst others because of color, smell, gels and black specks caused by binder and pigment degradation as well as incompatibilities between multiple polymers in multi-layers. The CIRCULAR FoodPack project strongly underscores that achieving closed-loop recycling of flexible packaging necessitates the use of **advanced physical recycling** methods. These include technologies such as delamination, de-inking, and dissolution-based recycling. Sections 3.1 and 3.2 of the deliverable detail the technologies developed within the project, focusing on delamination and de-inking in Section 3.1, and dissolution-based recycling in Section 3.2.

3.1. Delamination and deinking

Delamination and deinking can generally be divided into two main types:

1. Aqueous-based washing: This method involves using a mixture of water, typically heated to around 80°C, NaOH (sodium hydroxide), and a detergent. The combination effectively removes inks and adhesives from the material.
 2. Chemical wash: This approach adds chemicals, such as solvents or acids, to the medium. Alternatively, a completely solvent-based wash, which does not use water, can be applied to achieve ink and contaminant removal.
- CIRCULAR FoodPack has shown that the advantage of the former is that these water-based delamination/de-inking procedures can be implemented in currently existing mechanical recycling plants. Yet, such process has their limitations as it is not able to achieve delamination and de-inking of all common samples in flexible packaging such as multilayer flexible plastic packaging laminated by using conventional adhesives. Furthermore, from a safety perspective, the caustic concentration required to achieve efficient deinking is not attainable at present on the commercial setups. Therefore, in the project, delamination primers were incorporated successfully into the multilayer flexible packaging, which allowed to achieve delamination and de-inking of multilayer structures in such aqueous medium. These have the added benefit of exposing the adhesive layer as well to the deinking mediums removing these elements partly. The downside to this technology is that they are limited to applications that do not require pasteurization, retort or chemical resistance against certain product solvents. During the deinking trials, color staining, which is a re-adsorption of the (organic) colorants onto the packaging after release from the binder was thoroughly investigated here as well.. As a mitigation strategy, a de-inking process was developed using scavengers in the liquid that prevented the re-adsorption of colorants, thus avoiding color staining. Furthermore, curling of the flexible packaging impedes de-inking, and therefore mitigation strategies for 'curling' were developed, based on mastering conditions such as time, temperature and medium concentrations. Based on all these improvements, the project was able to demonstrate more than **95% removal of colorants** at scale when using well defined laminate feedstock.

- Alternatively, the project has shown that chemical delamination and de-inking offers more versatility to delaminate and deink samples with a broader range of common adhesives and ink binders. It is broadly applicable to the existing structures today but struggles with certain elements such as masterbatch coloring. Compared to a water-based medium, solvent-based delamination and de-inking processes were observed to achieve deeper cleaning of polymers and even repair defects from the water-based process, such as color staining issues. Because of the deep cleaning effect, such chemical/solvent based washing has high potential to achieve food safety standards compared to the aqueous washing. As a current disadvantage, Europe does not have large scale infrastructure yet to operate such a process, and even possibilities to perform such chemical washing steps at pilot scale is limited (which is why the project mainly upscaled aqueous based delamination and de-inking, as pre-treatment solutions before the mechanical recycling process).
- Next to delamination and deinking the project has demonstrated which Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) are present on flexible packaging, and has developed strategies to remove such VOCs, including improvements in the water-based washing process, as well as drying based in Infra-Red. The findings highlight an obvious yet very essential requirement to achieve clean PCR which is a thorough washing step to remove any surface contaminants from the original packaging content (e.g. food residuals) or contracted during the disposal, storage, collection or sorting. Any residuals that are not sufficiently removed will add to either the total VOC level or diminish the quality of the resulting recycle.

In general, an important learning is that delamination and deinking, whether with aqueous or chemical media, are essential steps to achieve higher quality recyclates with reduced gels content, black specks, or harmful VOCs. The effectiveness of this pre-treatment step is furthermore enhanced when combined with an extensive washing step removing any superficial contaminants from the original packaging content or contaminants caught during the disposal, collection and sorting processes. Higher quality PCR resins open the application window for flexible packaging with recycled content. This process thus is an essential building block to achieve recycling targets for flexible packaging. The chemical-based delamination & de-inking has more potential towards feedstock of unknown ink composition and food contact quality recycling compared to its traditional aqueous based counterpart but requires new recycling infrastructure in Europe.

3.2. Dissolution based recycling

Selective solvents are used in dissolution-based recycling to dissolve PE from post-consumer packaging waste, after which the undissolved residue (other polymers, paper, aluminum, adhesives, etc.) is removed, the dissolved PE is further purified from co-dissolved matter including volatile and non-volatile NIAS and IAS and finally dried and recovered as granulate.

Dissolution-based recycling thus enables the closed-loop recycling of unsorted or mixed waste streams with high proportions of non-PE foreign materials that cannot be processed into recyclates suitable for reuse in a closed loop by conventional mechanical recycling technologies or many chemical recycling approaches.

Furthermore, it was shown that dissolution-based recycling is also crucial for achieving particularly high recyclate purities, as in addition to the removal of foreign materials, for example from multilayer packaging, printing inks and other contaminants can also be effectively removed. This was demonstrated by a high reduction of semi-volatile and volatile contaminants in the challenge test and very low total VOC levels in the recyclates obtained from Loop 1. In addition, the high cleaning performance counteracts the formation of new degradation substances, such as odors during further processing. By using additional advanced purification units, this cleaning efficiency could be improved even further. This applies in particular to non-volatile contaminants, which cannot be effectively removed without the extractive cleaning of dissolution-based recycling. Despite achieving positive purification results, industrial scale infrastructure is not available yet and requires significant investment and commercialization, similar as for solvent-based delamination and deinking. At present, the demonstration plant used in CIRCULAR FoodPack is able to produce high quality recyclates at 25 kg/h.

However, the principle of dissolution-based recycling of waste polyolefin packaging plastics has been commercialized earlier. Based on former APK's technology there is a running capacity in Germany, currently in operation as LYB Solvent Recycling GmbH, Merseburg. Fraunhofer's dissolution technology, excluding advances in purification, has been operating in Indonesia since 2019.

3.3. Deodorisation after recycling as post-treatment

The KEYENBORG IR-Fresh® system for deodorisation and degassing of the VOCs of the PE PCRs after their recycling, consists of two steps. First the material is exposed to Infrared light in a rotating drum, followed by a hot air treatment in a conditioner. It can be applied batchwise or continuously anywhere at flake or pellet stage (at the recyclers, material suppliers, or producers). Such a dedicated treatment plant can also be established to upgrade the quality of the resins. During the project the **target of 95% odor reduction** for the upscaled recyclates has been reached with the PE PCRs deodorized with this advanced deodorization technology (TRL reached 6).

One of the key factors influencing the commercial success of a PCR resin is the level of SOIs⁴ (Substances of Interest) present, as producers closely scrutinize these levels. The additional cost

⁴ SOIs are chemical compounds or elements present in the resin that are closely monitored due to their potential impact on safety, quality, or regulatory compliance. For example, SOIs might include contaminants, additives, or residual chemicals that could affect the resin's performance, recyclability, or suitability for specific applications (such as food contact).

of pre- and/or post-treatment processes, compared to PCR resins with inherently lower contamination, will ultimately determine its market viability. Another critical qualifier for the treatment method is the throughput of the technology, which must be scaled to gain a competitive advantage. Currently, the IR-Fresh® technology supports continuous processing at a rate of up to 1.5 t/h.

3.4. Challenge test results for both recycling processes

Both mechanical recycling, combined with delamination and deinking purification, and dissolution-based recycling processes successfully purified and recycled artificially contaminated flexible packaging waste. The mechanical route proved effective in removing 81-98% of spiked contaminants, particularly excelling in the removal of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) but showed some limitations with larger molecules. In contrast, the dissolution process achieved more than 89-98% purification⁵, including the removal of molecules up to 390 g/mol, significantly enhancing its potential for PE PCR reuse in packaging for sensitive goods, including food applications.

For future challenge tests, adaptation and optimisation steps with regard to the analytical methods and decontamination processes will be essential. The detailed results and conclusions are reported in the public deliverable D4.4 “Challenge tests”.

4. DESIGN FOR AND FROM RECYCLING FOR CIRCULARITY OF FOOD PACKAGING VALUE CHAIN

The integration of advanced mechanically recycled post-consumer PE resin (PE PCR) in packaging is crucial for sustainable development. This section outlines strategies for optimizing PE PCR use in both food and non-food applications through effective design for and from recycling.

4.1. Key points

From a design **for** recycling perspective, the goal is to achieve a clean and pure material stream before reprocessing, ultimately producing high-quality recyclate resin for flexible applications when reprocessed. This can be achieved by implementing tracer-based sorting with tracer-doped ink, which ensures over 98% sorting efficiency using current commercial equipment. To further enhance the quality of recyclates, producers can use delamination primers in certain applications to facilitate delamination and deinking, thereby improving the removal of non-polyolefinic contaminants during wet treatment processes. Emphasizing surface printing as the primary printing form further aids in the removal of non-polyolefinic elements through aqueous deinking technologies. Additionally, in compliance with design for recycling guidelines, it is crucial to reduce any non-polyolefinic elements in the structure, such as adhesives, inks, binders, masterbatches, and lacquers, that could decrease the quality of the recyclate. This requires efforts from both producers of film materials and suppliers of raw materials for these producers, as improving some of these elements for recyclability is not yet fully enforced by law (CEN Guidelines for PPWR) and thus progresses slowly.

⁵ Removal efficiencies were most probably underestimated as concentrations in dissolution-based recycled PE were below the limit of detection.

From a Design **from** recycling perspective the objective is to incorporate high-content, pure PE PCR safely into packaging structures. Yielding high quality PCR can be achieved by ensuring thorough cleaning of PE PCR before and after reprocessing. As already explained above, a thorough washing process is the first essential step in removing any surface contaminants that would only add to the total VOC levels and further damage the mechanical and optical properties of the resulting recyclate film. It furthermore enhances the effectiveness of the subsequent wet treatment process such as delamination and deinking via aqueous or solvent based methods or solvent recycling. Here, the dissolution technique is effective for producing high-quality PE PCR, although it still struggles with complete deinking of black flexibles from non-food items. To enhance this process, the focus should be on synthesizing non-polyolefinic elements designed to improve removal efficiency. Additionally, deodorization via the project partner Kreyenborg process effectively reduces VOC levels to safe thresholds.

The incorporation of high-quality PCRs in significant amounts into film structures still presents several challenges. Although the methods described above enable the production of high-quality PCR resins, non-polyolefinic elements remain necessary in the film structure to meet specific packaging requirements. These include printing design (printing inks), bond strength (adhesive grade and grammage), hermeticity (plastomeric resin grammage, film thickness), and barrier properties (water vapor (WVTR⁶) and oxygen barrier (OTR⁶) achieved by using inorganic or organic materials). Consequently, there is a limit to the amount of PCR material that can be incorporated without compromising the performance of the packaging.

To further increase the PCR content, the PCR needs to be functionalized, such as in a machine direction-oriented film. Additionally, when incorporating mechanically recycled PCR resins in food contact applications, current regulations only permit this if the PCR is safely encapsulated between functional barriers. The implementation strategies for this will be described below.

4.2. Implementation strategies

4.2.1 General structures

Objective: Develop general adaptable structures that meet performance requirements while adhering to recycling guidelines.

Method: Thanks to the extensive efforts across other work packages, we have identified two general structures applicable to both food contact application (FCA) and non-food contact application (nFCA), which can be further tailored to specific application needs. By analyzing various input waste sources (referred as 3 loops in the project), we pinpointed constraints on packaging performance and the maximum allowable PE PCR content, leading to a balanced structure that prioritizes packaging performance while achieving a high PCR content of up to 34% for food and 50% for non-food packaging. Additionally, converting PE PCR into more functional forms, such as Machine-direction orientation polyethylene (MDO PE) film, offers the potential to further increase the overall PCR content in packaging. This approach has been demonstrated as feasible at a pilot scale, achieving a PCR content of up to 62% in non-food packaging applications.

⁶ WVTR: Water vapor transmission rate, OTR: Oxygen transmission Rate

Figure 1. General structures applicable to food packaging (left, triplex structure) and non-food packaging (right, duplex structure) for PE PCR (by advanced physical recycling) integration

For food contact applications, migration tests have clearly shown that Ethylene-vinyl alcohol (EVOH) and primered Silicon Oxide (SiOx) are the optimal solutions to achieve the required barrier for content preservation and SOI protection. Looking further down the lifecycle, other technologies can enhance the purity of the recycling stream. For example, using tracers to isolate a food contact stream, employing delamination primers to help cleaning agents during washing and deinking to reach inks that discolor and contaminate recyclate during reprocessing, and further purification with the CreaSolv® and Kreyenborg deodorisation processes.

Finally, the created films were successfully run on customer and OEM packaging lines and their various applications were given form through the creation of 6 different demonstrators (Figure 2 as described in Section 6).

4.2.2 Restrictions

The restrictions of PE PCR incorporation in flexible food and non-food packaging require to:

- Recognize limitations such as the maximum PE PCR content without compromising sealing or processability, and the application limits of novel technologies such as delamination primers.
- understand the dangers of offset migration that can compromise the safety of the product, during production and conversion.

These are discussed in detail below:

Maximum PE PCR content: The inclusion of advanced physically recycled PE Post-Consumer Recycled (PCR) materials in a structure is limited. A certain amount of virgin material is always necessary due to the nature of PCR. The recyclate typically consists of various grades and types of polyethylene (PE), such as LDPE and LLDPE, along with other minor materials. The blend of these components gives more general properties such as a low density (around 0.92 g/cc), melting points ranging from 110 to 130°C, and low modulus. In the packaging however, low melting points are often required to ensure proper sealing of packs. This can only be achieved with plastomers which are typically to be diluted in the recyclate blend. As such, a specific virgin resin is needed for this demand. Additionally, other elements like heat protective lacquers, delamination primers, printing inks, tracers, and barrier materials (e.g. EVOH, SiOx) are integral to the structure. These elements contribute to the technical criteria the final pack must meet and are not polyolefinic by nature.

Offset Migration Problem: Offset migration significantly restricts design freedom when incorporating PCR into the structure. More data is needed on the effects of coextrusion with PCR to determine if cross-contamination occurs at the extrusion level, which could render the extruded barrier film only non-Food Contact Approved (nFCA). This limitation currently confines designs to triplex formulations, where lamination must occur simultaneously to prevent offset migration on the reel.

Double Barrier: To safely contain any residual SOI from the purified PE PCR, the recyclate must be sandwiched between two functional barrier layers. This impacts the formulation of the film structure in several ways. Firstly, the adhesive must be carefully selected to cure slowly, allowing byproducts like CO₂ to diffuse out of the barrier gradually, thereby preventing bubble formation. Additionally, this adds complexity to the extrusion process, requiring intricate multilayer compositions and a finely tuned resin selection. If coextrusion is not used, sequential lamination steps are necessary to prevent offset migration.

Optimization of Novel Technologies on Conversion Line: Most of the technologies employed in this project are at an early Technology Readiness Level (TRL up to 5 or 6), meaning there are no optimized processing protocols for handling the materials yet. Over time, and with iterations on larger conversion lines, these protocols will have to be refined.

For example, during our initial run on the industrial conversion line, we observed that the residual solvent level of the DDP was too high, contributing to bubbling in the subsequent lamination stage and eventually resulting in a lower bond strength. Increasing the oven temperature during the application of the DDP should significantly mitigate this issue.

4.3. Recommendations

- **Flexible Food Contact Packaging:** Incorporate up to 30% PE PCR.
- **Non-Food Contact Packaging:** Incorporate up to 50% PE PCR. Possible further enhancement of the PE PCR content by implementation PE PCR in a functional way through the creation of for instance MDOPE with PCR.
- **Policy Support:** Encourage policies that support the development and adoption of these technologies to enhance recycling efficiency and sustainability. Standardize one approach using a combination of the best performing technologies as to ensure a stable and high purity recyclate stream can be generated.
- **Enhancement:** Advanced Chemical Recycling can and should complement these structures by providing an alternative for the virgin content that is inevitable in performing packaging structures.

4.4. Summary and conclusions

Establishing clear design guidelines for and from recycling that involve all relevant stakeholders is essential for enabling large-scale high-quality recycling and for fulfilment of the PPWR requirements. To support this implementation, the project partners adapted novel recyclable traceable flexible packaging designs for pouch manufacturing with PE PCRs. This involved the following key aspects:

- Extensive characterization of the created PE PCRs to benchmark them among best-in-class commercial grades into processing, purity and mechanical performance. Matching their performance for the right applications.
- Implementing PE PCR in a more functional way such as by the implementation in Machine directed oriented films
- Creating high purity recycling streams through the use of specific tracers in printing inks at very small quantities for separating food from non-food packaging during sorting
- Identification and exclusion of ink pigments leading to staining and bleeding issues during deinking in water-based media and use proper hot-washing process and anti-staining additives. Please note regarding the adoption of Technology on Existing Washing Lines: Not all concentrations were allowed to run on pilot lines due to safety concerns. Therefore, a tailored washing line has yet to be developed. Rolling out these lines to recyclers will be crucial, or a dedicated treatment plant with a specified line must be established to further purify certain streams.
- Integration of delamination/deinking primers for easy separation and functional barriers for safety
- Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCA/LCC/SLCA) of the novel packaging to quantify the overall environmental (including resource efficiency), economic and social impacts across the entire value chain, ensuring the most efficient and sustainable use of the PCRs

Adopting these strategies will significantly improve the use of PE PCR produced by advanced mechanical recycling in packaging, contributing to a more sustainable and efficient recycling process. Policymakers should support initiatives that promote these practices to achieve environmental and economic benefits.

Relevant research results are published in the public project deliverables D3.8 "Guidelines on Design for Recycling", D7.5 "Guidelines from final comprehensive sustainability assessment", and D8.7 "Business plan including exploitation, marketing plan, and financing needs for most promising technology".

5. SAFETY ASPECTS

Challenge tests performed for solvent-based purification technologies with contaminated PE based flexible packaging have yielded promising cleaning efficiency results (see Section 3.4). Still to enable the use of PE PCRs in food packaging for direct food contact applications, the project team developed functional barriers that effectively separate the recycle from the food-contact layers in new packaging structures (see Section 4.2.1)⁷. This approach utilizes a "double barrier," where PCR layer is sandwiched in-between to prevent set-off and ensure safety. These barrier layers are designed to fully cover and smoothen the PCR film surface, protecting the barrier layers from potential damage caused by particles.

⁷ see COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2022/1616 of 15 September 2022 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 282/2008, point (33), on page 7/44, functional barriers are to be considered under "novel technology".

Despite the fact that functional barriers were integrated in the structure that reduce migration considerably (see public deliverable D4.6), it should be highlighted that all experiments performed so far were done on flat sheets of packaging materials and not on the final (folded, sealed) pouches. Such conversion processes may introduce defects in the final packaging material that could influence migration, which was not investigated here. As the recycled materials contain contaminants of concern additional research would be needed to rule out a safety concern. Moreover, public deliverable D4.3 has shown that mutagenic compounds may be formed during mechanical recycling of waste, as evidenced by positive results in Ames tests. This was recently highlighted by other research consortia as well⁸ and underscores the need for a thorough understanding of such risks before mechanically recycled polyolefins are used in food packaging applications.

Further optimization and adaptation of the challenge test setup for PE flakes will be required, with the resulting findings, procedures, and insights contributing to ongoing standardization efforts. The combination of methods for the analysis of undesired and / or to be avoided substances due to toxicological concerns for input (packaging waste) / output (PE PCR) and challenge tests is essential for the assessment of the recyclates' quality. Further details on this topic are available in the public Deliverables D4.2, 4.3, 4.4 and 4.6.

6. IMPLEMENTATION OF CIRCULARITY INTO FOOD PACKAGING VALUE CHAIN

6.1. Food packages

Three different types of packages for food products were produced with the PE PCRs produced from the input flexible packaging waste from the business-to-business collection (Loop 2) and the waste from the tracer-based-sorted food packaging stream (Loop 3 in 2 cycles): These are the pillow bags for coffee beans (with Loop 3 Cycle 1 recyclates, L3C1), on Nestlé packaging line), gusseted bags for coffee beans (with Loop2 Cycle 1 recyclates, L2C1) as demonstrator by Amcor catalyst team and on Nestlé packaging line), stand-up-pouches for cocoa (with Loop 3 Cycle 2 recyclates, L3C2) as demonstrators by Amcor catalyst team). The demonstrators produced for the packaging of food are presented in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2. 6 Demonstrators; 3 for food packaging from left to right: coffee in pillow bag, cocoa powder in stand-up-pouch, espresso in gusseted bag, and 3 for non-food packaging from left to right: shampoo in sachet, detergent tabs in stand-up-pouch, wet-wipes in flow pack format

⁸ Mayrhofer et al. Safety assessment of recycled Plastics from post-consumer waste with a combination of a miniaturized Ames test and chromatographic analysis. *Recycling* 2023, 8, 87.

Functional barriers were integrated, choice of suitable barrier has been described in public deliverables D4.2 and D5.2. The tracer integration for sortability of food packaging from non-food packaging has been reported in deliverable D5.5, and detailed description of recyclate and laminate production has been described in D5.4 (confidential), and the pouch production has been summarised in D6.3 (confidential) for B2B scenario and in D6.4 (public) for traced food packaging scenario.

6.2. Non-food packages

The demonstrators produced for the packaging of non-food produced are presented in *Figure 2*. Three different types of non-food packages were produced with recyclates from Loop 1 (input waste: post-consumer flexible packaging household waste) and Loop 2 (input waste from business-to-business collection): shampoo sachet with Loop 2 material (demonstrator Amcor catalyst team), stand-up-pouch for detergent pods (Volpack line at Amcor with Loop 1 material), flow pack for wet wipes with Loop 1 material (demonstrator catalyst team). No functional barriers to prevent migration was needed.

6.3. Shelf-life simulation/calculation of packaged products

When developing a new packaging product, Nestlé conducts shelf-life simulations based on the packed product, pouch formats, and material types, utilizing equipment such as the Vertical Form Fill and Seal Rovema machine at Nestlé Research Lausanne. These simulations evaluate the moisture and oxygen sensitivity of the product to identify suitable food product types based on the barrier performance of the laminate and give an estimated product shelf-life duration.

It is important to consider that the design of forming shoulders and the cross-sealing jaw, during pouch production can impact barrier integrity, leading to potential barrier loss. To address this, oxygen (O₂) permeability and water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) measurements are performed on the 3D pouches after production. Residual gels in the laminate, excessive tension and sealing seams can also compromise the barrier, further underscoring the need for careful assessment.

In this project, novel flexible laminates containing PE PCRs were successfully applied to products such as roast and ground coffee and Nesquik cocoa powder. Shelf-life requirements were determined based on pack size and product type, with roast and ground coffee typically requiring an 18–24-month shelf life. However, for new materials offering sustainability benefits, depending on the product category, selling market, Nestlé could consider shorter shelf-life periods, such as 15 months, or in the worst case, 12 months, for the new product.

The CIRCULAR FoodPack pouches were deemed suitable for medium-sensitivity products. However, further improvements in barrier resilience are necessary for both flat materials and 3D pouches to ensure compatibility with higher-sensitivity products like pure soluble coffee.

6.4. Summary and conclusions

The applicability and processability of PE PCR containing flexible packaging materials have been validated in three use cases—home care, personal care, and food packaging—across five packaging formats: stand-up pouches, sachets, pillow and gusseted bags, flow packs. These innovative mono-material-based solutions, designed for both food and non-food applications,

have been successfully tested on existing Vertical Form Fill and Seal (VFFS) lines. They operated at competitive speeds within a reasonable sealing window, requiring only minor machine modifications. For applications with more demanding requirements, such as those requiring gas-tight packaging, enhanced solutions are necessary. Specifically, optimized sealing layers combined with tailor-made sealing jaws are essential to ensure bag integrity.

An important takeaway is the need for novel materials to be adaptable across a broad range of products. However, some packaging formats may not be able to incorporate the desired levels of PCR content, highlighting the need for further innovation and tailored solutions for specific applications. To maximize the impact of these materials, it is essential to optimize machinery and material performance for various packaging formats, enabling higher PCR content without compromising quality or efficiency.

7. CONSUMER ACCEPTANCE AND MARKET DEMAND

Consumer surveys have confirmed that the solution proposed by the project can be widely accepted by consumers once the introduction of the new material is accompanied by appropriate communication. Consumers are generally in favor of sustainable packaging, such as the solution offered by CIRCULAR FoodPack, and have a preference for recycled materials.

The new regulatory landscape is encouraging brand owners to adopt new standards, with PE PCR emerging as a viable option. Processors at different levels of the value chain have as well shown interest in the packaging approach proposed by the CIRCULAR Food Pack.

8. LIFE CYCLE SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT (LCSA)

8.1. Environmental sustainability (LCA)

- Compared to the conventional end-of-life option (incineration with energy recovery and landfill), the newly developed technologies (tracer-based sorting and/or advanced mechanical/physical recycling with purification) outperform for managing post-consumer flexible packaging waste. For example, per ton of PE-rich sorted household flexible packaging waste with advanced physical recycling using selective dissolution purification (CreaSolv®), resulting in flexible non-food packaging with 54% PE PCR, the climate change impact can be lowered by 27%.
- Compared to virgin non-recyclable flexible food packaging, replacing virgin materials with post-consumer recyclates (PE PCR) derived from household flexible packaging waste by 34% can considerably reduce the environmental impact (e.g. climate change impact reduction of 56% per m² of flexible food packaging). Increasing the recycled content in flexible food packaging (e.g., from 34% to 50%) on the other hand, may increase the environmental impact, in case the laminate specifications (such as thickness, surface weight and structure) need to be modified to support the higher recycled content. These modifications, if they result in a thicker and heavier laminate, may pose challenges to processability, especially during the sealing of the packaging.

8.2. Economic sustainability (LCC)

Both dissolution-based and water-based deinking technologies result in feasible business cases, giving competitive PE PCR costs to the virgin PE costs. Still, the conventional end-of-life option performs better cost-wise than the newly developed ones in CIRCULAR FoodPack project due to the lower waste disposal and the current affordable costs of the virgin materials. However, accounting for the potential revenue losses from not recycling PE-rich flexible waste could make the newly developed option more advantageous.

Below are some examples from 3 different scenarios:

- For example, per ton of PE-rich sorted household flexible packaging waste (non-recyclable with current infrastructure) with advanced physical recycling using selective dissolution purification (CreaSolv®), resulting in flexible non-food packaging with 54% PE PCR, the economic impact can be higher by 26%.
- For each ton of PE-rich recyclable business-to-business food packaging waste processed through advanced physical recycling with a water-based deinking cascade, resulting in flexible food packaging with 34% PE PCR, the economic impact can increase by 17%.
- In contrast, for tracer-based sorted food packaging from household waste, the economic impact per ton of PE-rich waste processed through advanced physical recycling with water-based deinking (or CreaSolv® purification/recycling), resulting in flexible food packaging with 50% PE PCR, can increase by 20%.

8.3. Regarding social sustainability (S-LCA):

- A notable level of positive social performance is evident throughout the value chain of the advanced end-of-life option.
- It is crucial to improve data availability on the upstream supply chain among the value chain actors.

A comprehensive Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) has been completed as part of the project and documented in Deliverable D7.5, titled “*Guidelines from Final Comprehensive Sustainability Assessment.*” This deliverable provides in-depth details on the three assessments, offering valuable insights and guidance for achieving sustainability objectives.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1. Addressing changes in the new PPWR

Packaging has emerged as a major source of waste and consumer dissatisfaction. Currently, it represents 40 percent of total plastic demand in the EU, with each European piling up approximately 180 kg of packaging waste annually. If this trend continues, plastic packaging waste in the EU is expected to rise by 46 percent. In light of these alarming statistics and the growing environmental crisis, the EU has introduced the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), which mandates that all packaging be recyclable by 2030. To promote plastic packaging circularity, PPWR focuses on high-quality recycling, ensuring that recycled materials retain their quality and can be reused in similar applications with minimal loss in functionality, quantity, or quality. A key element of the regulation is the increased incorporation of recycled

materials in plastic packaging. This requires PCRs to meet strict quality standards, making them suitable replacements for virgin plastics in equivalent applications. For instance, by 2030, PPWR mandates that polyolefin-based food packaging materials contain 10 percent recycled content, with this target rising to 50 percent by 2040.

The PPWR targets are ambitious, yet CIRCULAR FoodPack has demonstrated that they are achievable through a fixed cascade of physical recycling technologies to yield high purity PE PCR that should be paired with innovative, flexible packaging designs for and from recycling aiming at long-term sustainability criteria. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) findings from the project highlight that to make a substantial environmental impact, PCR content in flexible food packaging should reach as high as 34%, positioning the 2030 targets as a critical but interim milestone. Increasing recycled content in laminates—from 34% to 50%—can heighten environmental impact, as adjustments to laminate specifications (like thickness, surface weight, and structure) are necessary to accommodate the higher recycled content. These changes, if not properly optimized at the converters, may result in thicker, heavier laminates, which may complicate processing, especially in sealing. Economically, Life Cycle Costing (LCC) results indicate that post-consumer recycled polyethylene (PCR PE) will likely be more expensive than virgin PE. A calculation model further reveals that even with a maximum collection efficiency of 70 percent and chemical recycling efficiency of 60 percent, chemical recycling alone cannot fully meet the PCR quantities required according to the PPWR targets. This conclusion underscores the value of properly implemented physical recycling methods developed within the project, it enhances the need for a standardized protocol that can be widely implemented by stakeholders and the need for the legislation to provide incentives that value PE PCR (produced by advanced physical recycling) above virgin polymers. These are crucial to achieving these goals.

9.2. Further research needed

Research projects like this are vital for the industry and brand owners to improve practices, remain competitive, and explore innovative technologies. Continued research is essential to overcome remaining challenges, which include:

- **Improving practical applicability and industry standards:** Developing solutions that align with existing standards to support widespread adoption and seamless integration into the industry.
- **Building infrastructure and scaling up operations:** Establishing manufacturing pilot test lines to attract investors and operators while scaling up production to create sufficient material volume for suppliers. This process would provide valuable insights into operational efficiencies, resource requirements, and environmental impacts, enabling the optimization of recycling processes on an industrial scale.
- **Meeting PPWR 2040 requirements:** Addressing key circular packaging objectives, particularly for contact-sensitive applications, to comply with future regulations.
- **Standardizing risk assessment and testing frameworks:** Developing unified protocols, analytical tools, and centralized testing facilities (e.g., FDA-like labs) for the safe integration of PCR in contact-sensitive packaging. These efforts would build a robust knowledge base

and streamline regulatory submission processes, fostering safer and more sustainable packaging solutions.

- **Fostering collaboration across sectors:** Collaboration between industry stakeholders, research institutions, and government agencies to share knowledge and best practices and push for implementation of these best practices. Big brand owners and retailers should see the impending legislation as an opportunity to push for a more ambitious agenda and help create the change. They provide face/product to the consumer.
- **Addressing investment barriers:** Understand precisely investment barriers in the manufacturing and packaging industry – factors that hinder European and worldwide companies to move faster towards a reduction of fossil-based virgin material usage.
- **Consumer research and education:** Investigate consumer motivations and barriers to adopting sustainable behaviours, helping to design strategies that encourage widespread behavioural change.
- **Implementation of business-to-business waste collection systems for flexibles:** focusing on B2B collection for closed-system generation by brand owners, creation of specific recyclable stream for B2B collected waste for food packaging applicable PCRs
- **Evaluating alternative materials:** Further research into consumer-favored materials such as paper and carton, identifying opportunities for integrating these materials into sustainable packaging solutions.
- **Comparing recycling methodologies:** Undertake a detailed comparison of chemical and advanced physical recycling processes to evaluate their environmental, economic, and social impacts. Special emphasis should be placed on energy consumption, material recovery efficiency, and scalability. Incorporating factors such as resource criticality, future market dynamics, and regulatory shifts into sustainability assessments can enhance the reliability of long-term projections for circular packaging systems.

These focus areas will help address critical gaps, promote innovation, and align industry practices with evolving sustainability standards and consumer expectations.

9.3. Policy recommendations

Urgent action is needed to address regulatory, technical, and financial obstacles in the recycling industry, especially for food packaging materials. Below, the CIRCULAR FoodPack partners propose policies and investments in research and innovation, with which Europe can boost recycling efficiency, strengthen its competitiveness against recycled feedstock from outside the EU, promote sustainable practices, and uphold its leadership in environmental technologies. This will further advance European industrial sustainability, competitiveness, and resource independence.

9.3.1 Regulatory reforms

Advancements in sorting and recycling could be partially funded through Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) fees. However, these fees would be more effective if allocated according to the principle of 'earmarking,' ensuring they are directed toward building the necessary infrastructure for processing and recycling specific packaging types. For example, flexible

packaging waste faces challenges in recycling due to underdeveloped infrastructure in Europe, resulting in insufficient PCR of the required quality.

The PPWR requires further detailed legislation to formulate up-to date and standardised design guidelines, which are also expected to take into account advanced technologies. Additionally, advanced physical recycling technologies should be officially recognized as valid recycling solutions. This can be achieved by integrating the insights and developments presented in this deliverable, particularly those related to the newly developed CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies.

For implementation in food packaging, it is essential to streamline the legal approval process for recycled materials. A simpler and more efficient procedure would enhance market acceptance of circular packaging solutions and support the industry-wide transition.

9.3.2 Investment in the infrastructure

CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies, such as Tracer-Based Sorting, dissolution, and delamination/de-inking, offer significantly better performance when combined, compared to current mechanical recycling methods for flexible packaging. However, these technologies require scaling up to a commercial level. To support this transition, we advocate for a funding environment that promotes investment in large-scale waste sorting systems and infrastructure across Europe. This will ensure high-quality input packaging waste and adequate volumes for recycling. Financial support could include grants and subsidies to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) adopt sustainable packaging practices. Additionally, it is essential to incentivize the adoption of innovative sorting and recycling technologies, with a focus on further optimizing sorting lines for flexible packaging to enhance the quality of PCR-grade material.

To support the adoption of innovative sorting and recycling technologies, it is essential to offer incentives and subsidies that encourage investment in these solutions. Optimizing sorting lines for flexible packaging is a critical step, as it directly influences the quality of the starting material, which purification technologies can then use to produce high-quality PCR (by advanced physical recycling) material. Currently, packaging formats such as stand-up-pouches (SUPs), pillow bags, and other thicker materials that contain PCR are more difficult to sort compared to standard shrink wrap films, which can easily be separated from the rigid fraction. These newer types of packaging will pose additional challenges in sorting unless the sorting hardware is improved to accommodate them, making it crucial to invest in upgrading the infrastructure.

9.3.3 Investment in research and innovation

Funding is needed for research on contact-sensitive packaging and its circularity, focusing on advanced sorting, decontamination, and purification technologies (e.g. dissolution) and sustainable packaging design with PCR integration. Improvements are required both on the technological level (e.g. tracer technology, deodorization, delamination/deinking) and hardware level (e.g. scaling up production capacities, enhancing sorting apparatus) as well as further improvements on existing technologies (e.g. better recyclable adhesives, masterbatches that are extractable, ink pigments that do not bleed). R&D should also support machine adaptations, such as upgrading packaging lines to process recycled materials, through grants or co-financing. To accelerate technology development and scaling, public-private partnerships should be encouraged. Additionally, policy should promote information exchange and capacity-building initiatives to address shared challenges and drive innovation.

9.3.4 Industry standards

Innovation in the circular value chain for flexible packaging requires the standardization and harmonization of recycled grades and recycling processes, driven by industry organizations like CEFLEX or Flexible Packaging Europe. A key focus should be the standardization of machine-readable marking solutions for food-grade packaging that are accessible and accepted by brand owners, or a push towards a preferred option (a “one solution to adopt” for all). This is essential for separating food-only grades in flexible packaging waste management, as required by EFSA for circular food packaging. The industry must refine regulatory guidelines for recycling to ensure high-quality PCR is used sustainably, both for safe, convenient packaging and efficient circular waste management at the end of life. Additionally, targeted campaigns should be developed to educate consumers on the benefits of recycled and recyclable packaging, highlighting the environmental impact of recycling and the critical role consumers play in building a sustainable packaging ecosystem.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The CIRCULAR FoodPack project demonstrated the potential of advanced physical recycling technologies for flexible food packaging, focusing on innovative processes such as:

- **Tracer-Based Sorting (TBS):** Utilizing specific tracers in printing inks at very low quantities to separate food from non-food packaging during sorting.
- **Efficient Deinking and Delamination:** Achieved through water media and scavengers to remove inks and adhesives.
- **Thermal Deodorization:** Applied to recyclates produced by densification-extrusion-granulation, allowing the extraction of residual volatile organic compounds (VOC) from PE pellets.
- **Solvent based technologies:** Using the dissolution process for efficient material recovery as well as the advanced surface-cleaning via solvent-based deinking and delamination.

These advanced processes, incorporating CIRCULAR FoodPack technologies like TBS, deinking, dissolution, re-compounding, and deodorization, enable the production of high-quality PE PCR materials from flexible packaging waste, including both household and business-to-business streams. As a result, recyclable, traceable flexible packaging with over 50% PCR content can be produced. With newly designed functional barriers, these materials are suitable for contact-sensitive applications with 30% PCR content, broadening their use for demanding products. Despite the ambitious targets set by the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), these goals remain achievable and sustainable with coordinated efforts across the industry.

Effective circular recycling of plastic packaging waste, particularly plastic food packaging, is crucial for advancing environmental sustainability. However, the recycling industry faces significant regulatory, technical, and financial challenges that hinder its effectiveness. These barriers slow the transition to a circular economy and undermine Europe’s leadership in environmental technologies. Insights from the EU-funded CIRCULAR FoodPack project, which integrates expertise across the circularity chain—from sorting and purification to recycling and packaging design—highlight key challenges and areas of need.

Collaboration across the entire value chain—including collection, sorting, recycling, packaging conversion, and brand ownership—is vital to meeting legislative requirements, such as PCR content and design-for-recycling standards. Clear and consistent EU regulations, along with well-defined targets for flexible packaging and waste management, are key to enabling business predictability and mitigating financial risks and fostering investment in infrastructure. Furthermore, continued research is essential to addressing remaining challenges and ensuring the scalability and efficiency of these solutions.

